

Deliverable D6.1 Stakeholder engagement report

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1. Executive Summary

Deliverable 6.1 summarises the efforts of stakeholder engagement activities conducted throughout the project and how these have shaped the policy landscape and amplified the impact of the project. This deliverable thus highlights the extensive collaboration and communication actions undertaken to ensure the project's outputs and outcomes are **visible, influential, and impactful**, involving significant input from all partners across all work packages.

The BY-COVID consortium, comprising over 50 entities, systematically tracked dissemination, exploitation, and communication actions, contributing significantly to key performance indicators (KPIs) related to increasing the project's visibility, influence and impact. These included targeted stakeholder engagement, mentions in policy documents, presentations at high-level events, and various published works. A comprehensive list of actions is provided as an Annex, along with a summary of the interactions with relevant stakeholders in different areas.

The deliverable demonstrates how these sustained actions established or reinforced relationships with policy organisations, research infrastructures and related initiatives/projects of national and international scope.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Enable storage, sharing, access, analysis and processing of research data and other digital research objects from outbreak research	1. A research data management practice in European research infrastructures practice that drives discovery, access and reuse of outbreak data and directly links experimental data from HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02 transnational access projects into the COVID-19 Data Portal.	No
	2. Workflows and processing pipelines that integrate transparent quality management and provenance and are openly shared.	No
	3. Research infrastructures on-target training so that users can exploit the platform.	No
	4. Engagement so that stakeholders (RI, national centres, policymakers, intergovernmental organisations, funders and end-users) incorporate FAIR and open data in infectious disease guidelines and forward planning.	Yes
Objective 2 Mobilise and expose viral and human infectious disease data from national centres	1. A comprehensive registry of available data with established procedures to collate data governance models, metadata descriptions and access mechanisms in a pandemic scenario.	No
	2. Mechanisms for the initial discovery across data sources based on available metadata at the reference collection.	No
	3. Demonstrated transnational linking of real-world data from national surveillance, healthcare, registries and social science data that allow the assessment of variants to serve the research needs of epidemiology and public health.	No
	4. Demonstrated assessment of emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants against data generated in the ongoing European VACCELERATE clinical trials project to investigate vaccine efficacy.	No
Objective 3	1. A platform that links normative pathogen genomes and variant representations to research cohorts and mechanistic	No

<p>Link FAIR data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19</p>	<p>studies to understand the biomolecular determinants of variant response on patient susceptibility and disease pathways.</p> <p>2. An open and extensible metadata framework adopted cross-domain that supports comprehensive indexing of the infectious disease resources based on mappings across resources and research domains.</p> <p>3. A provenance framework for researchers and policy-makers that enables trust in results and credit to data submitters, workflow contributors and participant resources.</p>	<p>No</p> <p>Yes</p>
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>Develop digital tools and data analytics for pandemic and outbreak preparedness, including tracking genomics variations of SARS-CoV-2 and identifying new variants of concern</p>	<p>1. Broad uptake of viral <i>Data Hubs</i> across Europe delivers an order-of-magnitude increase in open viral variant detection and sharing.</p> <p>2. Infrastructure and quality workflows mobilised and shared to produce open, normative variant data that is incorporated into national and regional data systems and decision-making.</p>	<p>Yes</p> <p>Yes</p>
<p>Objective 5</p> <p>Contribute to the Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership and European Health Data Space (EHDS)</p>	<p>1. Guidelines and procedures for FAIR data management and access will be established, building on work of other guideline producing consortia such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), the 1Mio Genomes Initiative (1MG) and the Beyond One Million Genomes project (B1MG).</p> <p>2. Services, software, protocols, guidelines and other research objects that are openly accessible for reuse by the EOSC Association and the community at large as a foundation for European preparedness for infectious diseases, leveraging developments in EOSC-Life, SSHOC, EOSC-Future, EGI-ACE and other EOSC projects.</p> <p>3. Alignment (both policy and implementation routes) will have been achieved between the data governance strategies for routinely collected health data in the EHDS initiative, including the TEHDAS Joint Action and future EHDS Pilot Actions.</p> <p>4. To empower national centres to build capacity and train platform users and data providers (e.g., from life, social or health sciences), and with experts from across partner institutions collaborating to create training materials for the identified gaps, and to exchange experiences and knowledge.</p>	<p>Yes</p> <p>Yes</p> <p>Yes</p> <p>Yes</p>

3. Introduction

BY-COVID is a Horizon Europe-funded project that brings together a consortium of experts from clinical, public health, social and biomolecular sciences with a focus on infectious diseases. Its aims are to address key challenges in data-driven decision-making to support the ongoing response to COVID-19 and to enhance preparedness for future infectious disease outbreaks.

Work Package 6 of the BY-COVID project aimed to *engage, train and build capacity with national and international stakeholders, in support of building an efficient infrastructure for European preparedness for COVID-19 and other infectious diseases* (see Table 1 for an overview of related tasks). The purpose of this engagement with external parties was to ensure that the project, its outputs and its outcomes are **visible, influential, and impactful** through their uptake and/or endorsement during, and after the end of the project, in support of its long-term sustainability.

Deliverable 6.1 *Stakeholder engagement report* provides a summary of efforts and outcomes carried out during the project. Although contractually it reflects the actions described in Tasks 6.1, 6.2 and 6.3, all work packages and tasks across the BY-COVID project significantly contributed to stakeholder engagement, which was achieved through numerous dissemination, exploitation and communications actions. There was, additionally and in particular, a more formal collaboration with Task 7.4 *Outreach events to funders*, in the form of a policy impact event¹ in Brussels (held in December 2023), as well as a follow-on event, planned for September 2024.

It is also important to mention that, in the context of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), in December 2022, the EOSC Association launched an activity on Communication and Engagement, which BY-COVID representatives attended. It was agreed that the BY-COVID Communication Officer, resourced through WP7, was well placed to contribute to this task. Since then, most EOSC - BY-COVID engagement activities have happened through this WP (more information in the section on the EOSC Association and the developing EOSC Partnership).

Task 6.4 was, in contrast, more focused on *training and capacity-building* of users of BY-COVID outputs; its work and achievements are described separately in **Deliverable D6.2, The training efforts report**.

¹ <https://by-covid.eu/news/by-covid-research-innovation-policy-meeting/>

Deliverable 6.1 complements **Deliverable D8.3** *BY-COVID Long Term Sustainability Plan*, which provides a comprehensive overview of (1) key (exploitable) results (i.e. project assets, key outputs) and (2) their intended user base, as well as a roadmap for how they will be sustained after the project ends. A public list of key results is available on the project website², and it has been used to support stakeholder engagement.

Table 1. BY-COVID tasks related to Work Package 6 and **Deliverable D6.1**.

Task	Description	Comment
6.1	<i>Exchange knowledge and experience in relation to setting up surveillance systems for pathogens</i>	So-called “engage” tasks, and the natural home of Deliverable D6.1 <i>Stakeholder engagement report</i>
6.2	<i>Engage with the EOSC Partnership and the European Health Data Space</i>	
6.3	<i>Engage with intergovernmental policy-makers and funders</i>	
6.4	<i>Support and enable countries to train and build capacity</i>	See Deliverable D6.2 <i>The training efforts report</i>
7.1	<i>Delivery of communications strategy, website and branding</i>	Synergies with Deliverable D7.1 <i>Dissemination, exploitation and communication Plan</i> (Westwick et al, 2022)
7.2	<i>Industry engagement</i>	Detailed in D7.2 <i>Public report showcasing industry value from infectious disease data</i>
7.4	<i>Outreach events to funders</i>	Policy impact events, jointly with Task 6.3
8.4	<i>Development of long term sustainability plan for project outputs</i>	See Deliverable D8.3 <i>BY-COVID Long Term Sustainability Plan</i> for an overview of key results and their users. See also two policy briefs: Deliverables D8.4 (Blomberg et al, 2023) and D8.4 (second policy brief, working title)
All tasks	(from all Work Packages)	Carried out engagement actions (dissemination, exploitation and communications)

The main body of **Deliverable 6.1** (next section) begins with an overview of engagement efforts during the project, and of the mechanisms of engagement that were used. This is

² A public list is accessible at <https://by-covid.org/resources/>

followed by subsections for key selected stakeholders, using the structure shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Structure used to summarise engagement efforts for named stakeholders.

Subsection title	Description
Short description of the stakeholder Website Geographic scope (national-level, Europe, global)	About the stakeholder
Aim(s) of the engagement Relevant BY-COVID Task(s) or work package(s) BY-COVID focal partner(s)	About the engagement carried out
Summary of engagement activities and related outcomes	What BY-COVID did during the project
Next steps (if any)	What BY-COVID will do after the end of the funded phase, and by whom (if known)

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Overview of engagement efforts

Given the consortium's size (over 50 legal entities) and so as to keep track systematically of interactions with external parties, the consortium collectively contributed to a common spreadsheet recording actions of dissemination (including publications), exploitation and communications (see Table 3).

Table 3. High-level categorisation of stakeholder engagement mechanisms, along with their target groups and purposes. Adapted from European Commission (2023).

Mechanisms	Target groups	Purposes
Dissemination	Typically experts (academic, industry), including policy ones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To inform about the project results that are relevant to them, as they are created To foster impact for the project results, e.g. through increased awareness of project results, through training on how to use them, etc To make scientific knowledge a common good

Publications	Experts (usually researchers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This is a type of dissemination activity, conventionally treated separately from other dissemination activities To include peer-reviewed articles, as well as preprints
Exploitation	Users of the project's outputs, i.e. typically experts (academic, industry, policy-makers, civil society, etc) who are able to concretely use the project results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Represents the uptake/use of project results/outputs, usually by others outside of the consortium. Exploitation by the project consortium is also ok, e.g. as part of separate projects, etc This feeds directly into the long-term sustainability plan
Communications	Everyone	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To inform of the project Can be done at any time during project life

A range of stakeholder engagement mechanisms were employed, such as meetings, webinars, presentations, policy briefs, expert group membership, consultation responses, reports, case studies (Figures 1 and 2).

Figure 1. Mechanisms used for stakeholder engagement (October 2021 to September 2024)

Figure 2. Number of recorded actions targeting stakeholders (October 2021 to September 2024)

Figures 3 and 4 show targeted stakeholder groups and the engagement mechanisms employed. Together this collected information has been fed into project-level indicators, so as to track project performance and impact, as well as detect issues (e.g. stakeholders needing increased attention), gaps and opportunities (e.g. missing stakeholders, bias in engagement mechanism).

Figure 3. Stakeholder groups targeted between October 2021 to September 2024.

Figure 4. Selected examples of mechanisms employed during the project, for named stakeholders.

Published research works are a particular form of dissemination to experts. Peer-reviewed publications and preprints acknowledging project funding (e.g. the unique grant ID) and presenting project outputs were also reported collectively using a dedicated spreadsheet. This was supplemented by targeted searches in EuropePMC, to capture any that could be missing. A list is available on the project website³, with yearly tallies shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Peer-reviewed publications and preprints acknowledging project funding and presenting project outputs (October 2021 to September 2024)

³ <https://by-covid.eu/outputs>

Finally, BY-COVID organised a high-level event gathering together key opinion leaders in Brussels (Belgium) at the end of 2023, to discuss different perspectives on using open science to advance pandemic preparedness (Figure 6). A report is available⁴ that summarises the main outcomes from the discussions, organised around the themes of policy-making, industry and innovation, and research, as well as insights from funders and policy-makers who kindly provided keynote presentations. A follow-on event is planned for September 2024.

Figure 6. Policy-focused event⁵, organised by BY-COVID in December 2023, in Brussels, Belgium.

⁴ <https://by-covid.eu/news/by-covid-research-innovation-policy-meeting/>

⁵ <https://by-covid.eu/events/open-science-for-pandemic-preparedness/>

4.2 National surveillance systems for pathogens

4.2.1 National-level knowledge-exchange forums

Short description of the stakeholder:

Country-level stakeholders including ministry and government officials, clinicians and public health focal points, COVID data coordinators, among others.

Website: N/A

Geographic scope: national-level, Europe

Aim(s) of the engagement:

Facilitate the exchange of technical “know-how” on surveillance systems for pathogens, so that countries can more efficiently progress in their journeys toward operational and resilient infrastructures for preparedness.

Relevant BY-COVID Task(s) or work package(s): Task 6.1 *Exchange knowledge and experience in relation to setting up surveillance systems for pathogens*

BY-COVID focal partner(s): ELIXIR Hub, EMBL-EBI

Summary of engagement activities and related outcomes:

During the first half of the project, four online events were organised by the ELIXIR Hub, aiming to facilitate the exchange of technical “know-how” on surveillance systems for pathogens, so that countries could more efficiently progress in their journeys toward operational and resilient infrastructures for preparedness: 11th COVID-19 National Coordination Meeting (October 2021)⁶, 12th COVID-19 National Coordination Meeting (February 2022)⁷, 13th COVID-19 National Coordination Meeting⁸ and the 14th COVID-19 National Coordination Meeting⁹. These events represented the continuation of a prior similar effort organised by EMBL-EBI under the aegis of the European Commission (Open Science Unit), and attended by a range of country-level stakeholders including ministry and government officials, clinicians and public health focal points, COVID data coordinators, and many others.

Next steps (if any): With the pandemic slowing down its pace, the events were replaced by a new activity linked to establishing an ELIXIR Community of Practice on Pathogen Data (next section).

⁶ 11th COVID-19 National Coordination Meeting; [Agenda](#)

⁷ 12th COVID-19 National Coordination Meeting; [Agenda](#)

⁸ *National-level experiences of pathogen-related data- sharing in pandemic times and beyond*, June 2022; event page: <https://by-covid.org/news-events/pathogen-data-sharing/>

⁹ *National-level experiences of pathogen-related data- sharing in pandemic times and beyond*, November 2022; event page

<https://by-covid.org/news-events/pathogen-data-sharing-event-nov-2022/>

4.2.2 Community of Practice on Pathogen Data Platforms

Short description of the stakeholder:

Pathogen Data Platforms managers and those involved in regional/national-level activities within Pathogen Data Platforms, e.g. as bioinformaticians, data managers and stewards, data brokers, IT experts, legal experts.

Website: <https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/pathogen-data>

Geographic scope: national-level, Europe

Aim(s) of the engagement:

BY-COVID aims to engage with the ELIXIR Pathogen Data Focus Group, which was notably established as a result of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE SARS-CoV-2 data brokering platforms network funded under INFRADEV-03-2018-2019 and additional EC funding. In this task, eleven beneficiaries that were already part of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE activities have been meeting on a monthly basis to advance further on topics of joint interest between BY-COVID and the Pathogen Data Platforms community of practice.

Relevant BY-COVID Task(s) or work package(s): Task 6.1 *Exchange knowledge and experience in relation to setting up surveillance systems for pathogens*

BY-COVID focal partner(s): SIB, UiT, SciLifeLab, UniLu, SCIC, VIB, CNR, GOG, ALU-FR, EMC, UT

Summary of engagement activities and related outcomes:

- A Maturity Model for Pathogen Data Platforms¹⁰ was developed as part of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project. Within BY-COVID, we are running a pilot run with 11 participating institutions from around the globe, also beyond BY-COVID (AU, CH, EE, ES (2), FR, NO, SE (2), UK, US). The aim is to establish usability of such a maturity model, identify gaps in ensuring FAIRness by design, as well as identify the maturity criteria that need to be better explained. Two debrief sessions were organised in June to outline recommendations on the maturity model. Overall, participants found filling the maturity model a very rewarding exercise that also helped them identify a few gaps. Participants voted on the clarity of each criteria and rewordings will be proposed where needed. We also collected very interesting feedback and recommendations on how to diffuse the maturity model more broadly. All recommendations and the new version of the maturity model will be made publicly available.
- Additionally, the community has also started discussing bioinformatics gaps for Influenza analyses concerning resistance calling, and potential benchmarking needs for assembly and typing.

¹⁰ <https://elixir-europe.github.io/pdp-maturity-model/>

- Aitana Neves (SIB) participated in the BY-COVID “Open science for pandemic preparedness - accelerating research, innovation and policy-making”¹¹ event to discuss FAIR and open data sharing from the perspective of a global network of local pathogen data platforms.
- Aitana Neves (SIB) and L. Hugues (SciLifeLab) will participate in the “Maturity Model for Pathogen Data Platforms”¹² workshop planned in July 2024 to support capacity building.

The extra funding from the BY-COVID project has helped sustain and expand the network of pathogen data hubs that was established during the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project. Members from several nodes in the network have established the ELIXIR Pathogen Data Focus Group.

Next steps (if any): The BY-COVID Community of Practice will contribute to the Infectious Disease Toolkit (ITDk¹³) with a section on Pathogen Data Platforms, and will finalise the Maturity Model guidelines over the summer, in time for the end of the BY-COVID project. The Maturity Model for Pathogen Data Platforms¹⁴ will continue to grow in importance and numbers beyond the end of the BY-COVID project, and the Community of Practice will continue to engage with European and Global Pathogen Data Platforms to promote the adoption of this model.

4.3 Research infrastructures, projects and initiatives

4.3.1 Integrated Services for Infectious Disease Outbreak Research (ISIDORe)

Short description of the stakeholder:

ISIDORe¹⁵ is funded as part of the same set of COVID-19 “emergency calls” as BY-COVID¹⁶, and aims to accelerate the provision of research infrastructure services for rapid research responses to COVID-19 and other infectious disease epidemics. Coordinated by ERINHA,

¹¹ <https://by-covid.eu/news/by-covid-research-innovation-policy-meeting/>

¹² https://docs.google.com/document/d/1otOkxR6GIZamDIrFharf1Xn9JMD-kgJVJ0Webbu_gOg/edit

¹³ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org>

¹⁴ <https://elixir-europe.github.io/pdp-maturity-model/>

¹⁵ Research infrastructure services for rapid research responses to COVID-19 and other infectious disease epidemics, HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02, <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-infra-2021-emergency-02>

¹⁶ FAIR and open data sharing in support to European preparedness for COVID-19 and other infectious diseases, HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-01, <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-infra-2021-emergency-01>

the research infrastructure that federates maximum- and high-containment laboratories, this sibling project works to expand the resources made available to users, and to facilitate their access to cutting-edge services. If there is adequate stakeholder support, it may become a permanent capacity embedded in the EU's overarching strategy for pandemic preparedness and crisis management.

Website: <https://isidore-project.eu/>

Geographic scope: national-level, Europe, International

Aim(s) of the engagement:

Ensure technical synergies between the two projects, as specified in the calls funding BY-COVID and ISIDORe.

Relevant BY-COVID Task(s) or work package(s): Task 3.4 *Integrate open research data from INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02 WP2 Accessing heterogeneous data across domains and jurisdictions for enabling the downstream processing of COVID-19 and future pandemic episodes data*

BY-COVID focal partner(s): ERINHA

Summary of engagement activities and related outcomes:

Actions capitalised on the involvement of several research infrastructures and organisations (e.g. ERINHA, ELIXIR, INFRAFRONTIER, INSTRUMENT, EUROBIOIMAGING) in both projects. There was a broad collaboration to operationalise data flows from ISIDORe Transnational Access projects into the COVID-19 Data Portal. Umbrella Data Management Plans (David et al., 2023) were co-created to integrate FAIR data in the context of pandemic preparedness, paving the way for national and international research infrastructures and research organisations to have foundation-level data management skills and policies.

Next steps (if any): Definition of Minimum Metadata Requirement for pandemic preparedness research data, allowing the definition of the mandatory, desirable and optional metadata required in different cases of uses, in several contexts and disciplines (with recommendations formalised in a paper planned in the framework of ISIDORe). Another paper on data mobilisation processes, led by the BY-COVID partners will propose recommendations for more efficient data mobilisation processes using these metadata requirements (in preparation).

4.3.2 European Virus Archive Global (EVA-G)

Short description of the stakeholder:

EVA Global (EVA-G) is a non profit organisation that mobilises a global network with expertise in virology to collect, amplify, standardise, characterise, distribute, track authenticate viruses and derived products.

Website: <https://www.european-virus-archive.com>

Geographic scope: Europe, international (25 laboratories, 16 EU members and 9 non-EU institutions)

Aim(s) of the engagement:

Ensure technical synergies between the two projects

Relevant BY-COVID Task(s) or work package(s): Task 6.1 *Exchange knowledge and experience in relation to setting up surveillance systems for pathogens*

BY-COVID focal partner(s): IZSve, IZSLER

Summary of engagement activities and related outcomes:

EVA-G deals with animal and zoonotic viruses, including SARS-CoV-2 strains, biobanking and data sharing. The collection of SARS-CoV-2 variants and related products is listed in a regularly-updated public online database, part of the EVA website. The website recently added a new section dedicated to antiviral compounds test results. Both EVA-G and BY-COVID operate in the context of pandemic preparedness, paving the way for national and international research infrastructures and research organisations to have foundation-level data management skills and policies. They support fair and equitable benefit sharing and are actively implementing a compliance strategy for the CBD/Nagoya protocol.

At the first annual EVA-G meeting in Paris (June 2022), a BY-COVID representative presented the project, emphasising the sharing of data and metadata related to SARS-CoV-2 variants. BY-COVID representatives also attended all subsequent EVA-G meetings, including the consortium-wide meeting in Padua (2023) and focused events such as the PI-centred meeting in Brussels (January 2024) and the sensitive data/DURC meeting in Amsterdam (November 2023). During the final EVA global meeting in Marseille, June 2024) a BY-COVID representative presented success stories from the projects and explored areas of mutual interest, including data migration between the two projects.

Next steps (if any): The EVA Global Consortium's EC funding will end in September, 2024. The members are evaluating how to sustain the infrastructure and results obtained (3,800 references in the catalogue, 2,600 virus strains, 5,200 online enquiries). EVA coordinated the successful HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01-04 application *European Viral Outbreak Research Alliance* (EVORA) that brings together EVA, the BY-COVID coordinator Elixir and the ISIDORE coordinator ERINHA. BY-COVID was represented at the EVORA kick-off meeting (Brussels, January 2024). It is expected that the established synergy among the 3 infrastructures will facilitate the sharing of resources in the future.

4.3.3 Korea Research Institute of Standards and Science (KRISS)

Short description of the stakeholder:

The Korea Research Institute of Standards and Science (KRISS) is a government-funded national measurement standards laboratory for the Republic of Korea also responsible for advancing measurement technologies. KRISS plays a pivotal role in upgrading Korea's main industries to the global level by research, development and dissemination of measurement science and technology.

Website: <https://www.kriss.re.kr/eng/>

Geographic scope: East Asia

Aim(s) of the engagement: KRISS will encourage the deposition of SARS-CoV-2 and other viral genome sequences from KRISS, its research partners and Korean institutes, including the Korea National Institute of Health (KNIH), to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA).

Relevant BY-COVID Task(s) or work package(s): Task 6.1 *Exchange knowledge and experience in relation to setting up surveillance systems for pathogens*

BY-COVID focal partner(s): EMBL-EBI

Summary of engagement activities and related outcomes: Initial contact between EMBL-EBI and KRISS was taken up in 2023, but as the partners have since been waiting for the formal signing of the amendment, no further activity took place.

Next steps (if any): Remain engaged with KRISS until the end of BY-COVID and attempt some sequence routing to the ENA as agreed.

4.4 Broader thematic areas

4.4.1 Journal Publishers

Short description of the stakeholder:

In 2020 the Wellcome-coordinated COVID-19 statement¹⁷ was signed by over 30 publishers calling for open or free access to all COVID-19 publications for the duration of the pandemic; for COVID-19 papers to be made available via preprint servers prior to journal publication; and data from COVID-19 research to be shared as early as possible. To implement these commitments, the COVID-19 Rapid Review Initiative¹⁸ was launched by a group of publishers and related organisations, including resources from BY-COVID.

¹⁷<https://wellcome.org/press-release/sharing-research-data-and-findings-relevant-novel-coronaviruses-ncov-outbreak>

¹⁸<https://www.oaspa.org/news/guest-post-covid-19-rapid-review-initiative-an-update-to-our-statement-of-intent>

Website: The *Scholarly Communication in Times of Crisis: The response of the scholarly communication system to the COVID-19 pandemic* report¹⁹.

Geographic scope: Global

Aim(s) of the engagement:

UOXF participated in the COVID-19 Rapid Review Initiative, with major publishers and other research groups focussing on improving scholarly communication; the result is a report that presents the results of research undertaken by the authors and reviews research conducted by others, with a view to identify opportunities for the scholarly communication stakeholders to effect change that will extend beyond the pandemic and have long-lasting benefits. The sharing of the SARS-CoV-2 genome is seen as the poster child for open science, and the pandemic held up as a turning point for open science. Yet the report finds this early promise has only partly been realised. Levels of COVID-19 research data sharing remained low during the pandemic, and preprinting of research on the virus has not been as common as hoped. The report makes a series of key recommendations, three of which focus on opening up data, encouraging pre printing, and strengthening collaboration across the scholarly communication ecosystem. The report concludes that there is no magic bullet to improve scholarly communication. It is a joint responsibility that requires collaboration and coordinated action across stakeholders in the research system.

Relevant BY-COVID Task(s) or work package(s): Task 6.3 *Engage with intergovernmental policy-makers and funders*

BY-COVID focal partner(s): UOXF (ELIXIR-UK) and FAIRsharing

Summary of engagement activities and related outcomes:

The data policies of the journal publishers of this initiative were grouped and made visible under a dedicated FAIRsharing Collection²⁰, which includes 14 policies that recommend a total of 137 data repositories and that refer to 27 (meta)data standards. In addition, to guide journal publishers to improve their policies to what they recommend in terms of standards and data resources, FAIRsharing developed a tailored Educational infosheet²¹.

Next steps (if any): The work to improve journal publishers data policies continues in FAIRsharing under several other Horizon Europe projects, such as TIER2 (in a pilot with publishers²²) and the collaboration with FAIR-Impact²³, as well as a collaboration with UKRN²⁴.

¹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.17125394.v1>

²⁰ <https://beta.fairsharing.org/C19RR>

²¹ <https://fairsharing.org/educational#publishers>

²² <https://tier2-project.eu/pilots/8>

²³ <https://blog.fairsharing.org/?p=668>

²⁴ <https://blog.fairsharing.org/?p=691>

4.4.2 Industry engagement

Short description of the stakeholder: Industry (SMEs and large enterprises), including industries around diagnostics, drug or vaccine development, biotech, bioinformatics (DaaS and SaaS provider), consulting, CRO/CMO.

Website: N/A

Geographic scope: International as the companies could have headquarters outside Europe, but they have presence in the European market.

Aim(s) of the engagement:

Identification of users or potential users of the BY-COVID resources, as these resources are freely available online, in order to demonstrate the impact of open data during and beyond the COVID-19 pandemic to develop medicines, diagnostic tests and other innovative products relevant to infectious diseases.

Relevant BY-COVID Task(s) or work package(s): Task 7.2 *Industry engagement*

BY-COVID focal partner(s): ELIXIR Hub, UU

Summary of engagement activities and related outcomes:

To foster a community of specialists to discuss visionary ideas, challenges, and solutions in the field of COVID and infectious diseases, we launched an online survey²⁵ in 2022-2023. This survey invited companies to share their experiences with working on COVID-19 open access data. Despite the ELIXIR and UU efforts through social media, newsletters (more than 1500 subscribers), and direct contacts to almost 100 companies, only 20 responses were received, showing limited interest on the topic of open data in infectious diseases. In addition, until March 2024 two industry related events were organised:

- 24th of January 2023: virtual access day²⁶ entitled “Data driven innovation in infectious diseases”, organised by UU. This event was attended by 58 participants (seven industry participants (12%)), five invited industry flash talks speakers). This event hosted two roundtable discussions on “Repurposing data & software tools” and “Novel technologies”.
- 6th of December 2023: F-2-F high-level event²⁷ organised by ELIXIR, entitled “Open science for pandemic preparedness” to discuss the value of open data and tools in addressing the COVID pandemic and future pandemics with experts from the European Commission, industry and academia. This event was attended by 45 participants (six industry participants (13%)), three invited industry speakers, One

²⁵ <https://uk.surveymonkey.com/r/ZXF6SCV>

²⁶ <https://by-covid.org/news-events/by-covid-accessday/>

²⁷ <https://by-covid.org/events/open-science-for-pandemic-preparedness/>

session was dedicated to industry presentations showcasing the impact of Open science in the infectious disease industry.

Next steps (if any): By the end of the project, one last F-2-F event will be organised by ELIXIR and UU in September 2024, engaging industry and policy-makers. Until then, companies are invited to contribute to the ITDk, showcasing methods and technologies developed during the COVID-19 pandemic which could be useful for future health outbreaks. Also, the industry speakers of the previous events are invited for interviews to understand the usage of open data in their innovative products which will enrich the public report D7.1. The experience built from these activities will enrich ELIXIR and EATRIS industry engagement activities and would be used in the European Viral Outbreak Research Alliance (EVORA project)²⁸.

4.4.3 Engagement with the Social Sciences

Short description of the stakeholder:

Representatives of the European social sciences repositories, EUI and partner institutions engaging with wider social sciences networks (researchers, data curators, data holders, international data organisations etc.)

Website: N/A

Geographic scope: European/international

Aim(s) of the engagement:

- Raising awareness on the critical socioeconomic factors influencing policy-making and uptake of measures in relation to COVID-19 and other infectious diseases.
- Enhancing multi-disciplinarity in view of harmonising metadata and /or data discovery process when dealing with pandemics phenomena from an interdisciplinary perspective.
- Familiarising broader scientific fields coming from health and natural sciences with social science data and the way to collaborate together in order to deal with future pandemics.
- Interdisciplinary approaches to be discussed when dealing with legal and ethical aspects of socioeconomic and health data.

Relevant BY-COVID Task(s) or work package(s): WP2/T2.4, WP5, WP6

BY-COVID focal partner(s): CESSDA MO and affiliated entities (ADP, EKKE, KNAW-DANS), EUI

Summary of engagement activities and related outcomes:

²⁸ <https://evora-project.eu>

- Integration of three data sources under the social sciences and humanities section²⁹ of the COVID-19 data portal.
- Contribution to the socioeconomic data sources³⁰ section of the IDTk.
- Roundtable during the 2022 GA meeting of BY-COVID project.
- “National-level experiences of pathogen-related data sharing in pandemic times and beyond”, 25 November 2022, Open online meeting on exchanging national experiences (technology and policy aspects) on data sharing during the COVID-19 pandemic. CESSDA participation focused on knowledge exchange/solving bottlenecks across sectors, including social sciences.
- Workshop during 5th Consortium Meeting, 10 October, 2023 in Barcelona entitled “BY-COVID-GDPR Workshop” coordinated by Patricia Palagi (SIB), Dimitra Kondyli (CESSDA/EKKE), Irena Vipavc Brvar (ADP), Salvador Capella (BSC), Simon Saldner (DANS), and Vasso Kalaitzi (DANS). Issues related to data management compliance with GDPR have been discussed. Challenges and opportunities raised from natural/health sciences and social sciences have been discussed.
- Research data management (RDM) training: Preparing to manage your data across disciplines, 2023³¹ (delivered in collaboration between social science and health infrastructures, 3 webinars). The webinars focused on research data management to be accessible to the research communities along with good RDM practices.
- BY-COVID Spring 23 Use Cases Workshop: Integration of socioeconomic data in observational studies on vaccine effectiveness (Vasso Kalaitzi, Nina van Goethem, & Simon Saldner. (2023))³²
- BY-COVID Spring 23 Use Cases Workshop: Integration of socioeconomic data in observational studies on vaccine effectiveness (1.0). [Workshop report]³³
- BY-COVID Spring 24 Baseline Use Case Workshop: Integration of individual-level socioeconomic data for infectious diseases research and prevention in Europe [event³⁴]
- BY-COVID Spring 24 Baseline Use Case Workshop: Integration of individual-level socioeconomic data for infectious diseases research and prevention in Europe [workshop report³⁵]

²⁹ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/search/social-sciences>

³⁰ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/data-sources/socioeconomic-data>

³¹ <https://by-covid.org/events/research-data-management-training/>

³² https://www.cessda.eu/News/CESSDA-Newsitem-nid3566?utm_source=newsletter&utm_medium=email&utm_campaign=cessda_newsletter_launching_our_strategy_2023_2027&utm_term=2023-10-09

³³ <https://zenodo.org/records/8234104>

³⁴ <https://by-covid.org/news-events/spring-2024-baseline-usecase-workshop/>

³⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/12168495>

- Integration of socioeconomic data in observational studies using a prototyped workflow standard to federated population health research (WP5). Draft due July 2024^{36]}
- BY-COVID Fest: training in data sharing and reuse under GDPR, and IDTK contentathon³⁷ (Saldner et al. 2024).

Next steps (if any): Based on the examples of socioeconomic data sources integrated into the COVID-19 data portal, more relevant data sources could in the future be integrated under the relevant categories. Furthermore, the engagement with the social sciences and humanities under the BY-COVID project can lead to further future engagement with regards to enhancing research, policy making and broader public awareness in relation to infectious diseases by also taking into account socioeconomic data factors.

4.5 Policy Sphere

4.5.1 European Commission

Short description of the stakeholder:

European Commission, particularly the unit focused on Open Science and Research Infrastructures

Website: N/A

Geographic scope: Europe

Aim(s) of the engagement:

Support the European Commission in its efforts to coordinate various relevant strands of work funded by different projects on surveillance systems for pathogens

Relevant BY-COVID Task(s) or work package(s): WP1 *Support for virological analyses in emerging disease outbreaks* ; Task 6.2 *Engage with the EOSC Partnership [and the European Health Data Space]* ; Task 6.3 *Engage with intergovernmental policy-makers and funders*

BY-COVID focal partner(s): EMBL-EBI, ELIXIR Hub

Summary of engagement activities and related outcomes:

Since the very beginning of the pandemic, the European Union has been funding a number of projects on surveillance systems for pathogens, such as that causing COVID-19. In particular, it has supported improvements and expansion of flagship bioinformatics resources such as the COVID-19 Data Platform³⁸, which itself consists of three connected components (the COVID-19 Data Portal, SARS-Cov-2 Data Hubs, and the Federated European Genome-Phenome Archive) hosted by EMBL-EBI. Bi-weekly coordination calls

³⁶ docs.google.com/document/d/119iCUbqG_WDEG4Do8phYrbWSwC6mHIzL4h0AUIAsLRg/edit

³⁷ <https://by-covid.org/events/by-covid-fest/>

³⁸ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/the-european-covid-19-data-platform>

bringing together EMBL-EBI, ELIXIR and the *Open Science and Research Infrastructures* Unit were hence held to coordinate and align efforts across various funding streams³⁹ - the value of such interactions was highlighted by the Unit during the Open science for pandemic preparedness event⁴⁰ (Brussels, Belgium, December 2023). Thanks to facilitation by the Unit and the existence of the BY-COVID Consortium, project experts were able to quickly compile and provide information on 'long COVID' to the Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety DG SANTE in January 2023.

Next steps (if any): ELIXIR Hub will continue to participate in the weekly coordination meetings with the EC . Further engagement with EC stakeholders is planned on a dedicated BY-COVID policy event on 11th September 2024.

4.5.2 EOSC Association and the developing EOSC Partnership

Short description of the stakeholder:

EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) was envisioned as a key enabler for Open Science in Europe, supporting researchers in sharing and exploiting research products (e.g as data, publications, and code) through value-added horizontal (i.e. cross-disciplinary) and thematic (i.e. discipline-specific) services. EOSC was developed in an initial implementation phase from 2016-2020 under Horizon 2020 and is being expanded in a second implementation phase via the EOSC Partnership from 2021-2027 under Horizon Europe. The Partnership brings together institutional, national, and European initiatives, as well as other relevant stakeholders, to co-design and implement an European Research Data Commons in which data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). The Partnership includes the European Commission, the EOSC Steering Board and the EOSC Association. The EOSC Steering Board is an expert group consisting of representatives of the 27 European Member States and Associated Countries that represents the interests of the EOSC stakeholder community and advises the European Commission in the development and implementation of EOSC. In this frame, the EOSC Steering Board has developed the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) to advise the European Commission on the development and implementation of EOSC.

In summary, the EOSC Tripartite Governance consists of representatives from the EOSC Association, the European Commission and the EOSC Steering Board. The EOSC Tripartite Governance is a concept of strategic coordination between the EU, represented by the Commission, the EOSC Association, and the Member States and Associated Countries, involved in the EOSC Steering Board.

³⁹ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/partners?activeTab=Funding%20projects>

⁴⁰ <https://by-covid.eu/news/by-covid-research-innovation-policy-meeting/>

The EOSC Association is also the project coordinator for the Horizon Europe-funded EOSC Focus project, which supports the whole Partnership, with the EOSC-A Secretariat⁴¹ being the project coordinator. The aim of the EOSC Association is to steer coordination to leverage the EOSC ecosystem.

Website: <https://eosc.eu>

Geographic scope: Europe

Aim(s) of the engagement:

Create/strengthen communication channels so that research infrastructures can convey EOSC-related input to the EOSC Partnership.

Relevant BY-COVID Task(s) or work package(s): Task 6.2. *Engage with the EOSC Partnership [and the European Health Data Space]*

BY-COVID focal partner(s): CSIC, CIRMMP, ELIXIR Hub

Summary of engagement activities and related outcomes:

The EOSC Association developed a Handbook for Effective Collaboration within the EOSC co-programmed Partnership⁴² in order to assist INFRAEOSC-funded projects and neighbouring projects partners, coordinators, and work package leaders by providing operational mechanisms to coordinate their activities in the context of the Partnership.

One of the areas of this Vademecum is the “Communication and Stakeholder Management” section. Among the relevant actions implementing the guidelines of the Vademecum, there was the creation of a Communication and Engagement Working Group, in order to engage with members of each Horizon Europe ongoing project. The Engagement WG holds a monthly meeting where project representatives give an update on the progress of their respective project as well as on the communication or engagement activities being carried out, nationally and at the European level. This has provided an advantageous coordination among the initiatives of the many active projects addressing the EOSC Association and the EOSC partnership.

Another relevant avenue of communication implemented by the EOSC Association is the EOSC Forum⁴³. The EOSC Forum is described in the Vademecum as the community engagement platform, playing a pivotal role in the implementation and execution of the interaction activities with the EOSC Association. In particular, the Forum hosts a specific section for the activities of the aforementioned HE Communication & Engagement group. The Forum permits the dissemination of the initiatives discussed in the WG meetings along with other relevant actions and achievements. In addition, documents can be distributed

⁴¹ <https://eosc.eu/secretariat/>

⁴² <https://eosc.eu/sites/default/files/2022-10/Vademecum%20HE%20EOSC-related%20Projects.pdf>

⁴³ <https://forum.eosc.eu/login>

via the forum, such as project reports. The members of this Forum subgroup include representatives of all the partners involved in Task 6.2.

The main person actively attending the online WG meetings is Elaine Harrison, from ELIXIR, who has also contributed several posts to the Forum.

Next steps (if any): ELIXIR-Hub will keep attending the EOSC Focus Communication and Engagement Working Group monthly meetings.

4.5.3 European Health Data Space (EHDS)

Short description of the stakeholder:

The European Health Data Space is an EU Regulation approved in April 2024, aiming to empower individuals through better access to their health data, supporting free movement of health data with people and setting up rules for use of health data for research, innovation, policy making. Thus, the EHDS is not a stakeholder group in itself, but is crucial for many digital health stakeholder groups - especially citizens, health professionals, researchers and regulators/policy makers. Engagement activities in this regard mean disseminating BY-COVID work in EHDS-related occasions.

The Joint Action Towards the European Health Data Space (2021-2023) aimed to develop European principles for the secondary use of health data. The main results include the development of a quality framework, recommendations on SPEs, stakeholder engagement exercises, and recommendations based on an EU-wide citizen consultation on the secondary use of health data. The second Joint Action Towards the European Health Data Space (TEHDAS2, 2024-2026) aims to develop guidelines and technical specifications for common use by all Member States and the European Commission towards implementing secondary use of health data. This Joint Action will be key for all stakeholders in the European health data landscape as it will define description duties (metadata) and access procedures.

Website: https://health.ec.europa.eu/ehealth-digital-health-and-care/european-health-data-space_en & <https://tehdas.eu/>

Geographic scope: EU

Aim(s) of the engagement:

Ensure alignment (policy and implementation routes) with the data governance and use strategies set out by the EHDS Regulation - especially regarding routinely collected health data and infectious disease data.

Relevant BY-COVID Task(s) or work package(s): Task 6.2. *Engage with the [EOSC Partnership and the] European Health Data Space)*

BY-COVID focal partner(s): EMPIRICA, Sciensano

Summary of engagement activities and related outcomes:

Engagement with EHDS stakeholders happened above all through:

- updating the consortium on EHDS developments - e.g. in final general assembly meeting;
- disseminating BY-COVID in EHDS-themed events and exchanges;
- linking health-related EOSC topics to EHDS.

The table below includes the EHDS stakeholder engagement efforts undertaken during the project:

Short Description	Audience, size	Place and Date
Presentation on EHDS Regulation to BY-COVID WP6 partners	BY-COVID WP6 Partners; ~20	May 2022
Hybrid Event by DigitalHealth Hub Greifswald (Germany) on EHDS, mention of BY-COVID, linking to the project website, at ⁴⁴	digital health researchers, clinicians and digital health industry representatives, mostly from Germany; 100-200	18 August 2022
TEHDAS project forum #3 - Mentioned BY-COVID and its relation to EHDS, especially regarding metadata and data quality; mention in the breakout room on data quality in the EHDS regulation proposal ⁴⁵	representatives of Horizon20202 and HorizonEurope projects, as well as from national health authorities and research; 100-200	22 June 2022, online
EOSC Symposium 2023: Session "EOSC contribution to the EU Missions & Partnerships". Session chairing by Marieke Willems (ELIXIR), presentation by Nadim Rahman (EMBL-EBI). Mention of links to EHDS, jointly with EOS4 Cancer speaker Salvador Capella Gutierrez ⁴⁶	Researchers, EOSC project representatives; 100-200	20 September 2023, Madrid
BY-COVID Fest 2024: Session on anonymisation, focussing also on health data anonymisation in EHDS Regulation ⁴⁷	Researchers, ca 20 attendees	24 January 2024, Athens

Next steps (if any):

Considering the EHDS regulation approval on 24 April 2024, next steps until project end would be to:

⁴⁴<https://www.digitalesmv.de/veranstaltungen/meet-discuss-create-ehds-mii-ths-diz-leicht-erklaert-gesundheitsdaten-fuer-die>

⁴⁵<https://tehdas.eu/event/project-forum-3/>

⁴⁶<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5eQJqU0qfBc>

⁴⁷<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11220597>

- Monitor stakeholder reactions with regards to infectious disease data and routinely collected health data
- Disseminate the BY-COVID citizen engagement material to help raise awareness of secondary use of health data
- Bring the results of BY-COVID project to the attention of the competent authorities in TEHDAS2

4.5.4 Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)

Short description of the stakeholder:

The OECD is an intergovernmental organisation focused on shaping policies that foster prosperity, equality, opportunity and well-being for all. Its Global Science Forum (GSF) aims to support countries to improve their science policies and share in the benefits of international collaboration.

Website: <https://www.oecd.org/sti/inno/global-science-forum.htm>

Geographic scope: global

Aim(s) of the engagement:

Ensure that the BY-COVID project and its outputs are visible to policy-makers (especially those dealing with research infrastructures), and ideally appreciated and endorsed.

Relevant BY-COVID Task(s) or work package(s): Task 6.3 *Engage with intergovernmental policy-makers and funders*

BY-COVID focal partner(s): ELIXIR Hub

Summary of engagement activities and related outcomes:

Supported their project on *Very Large Research Infrastructures* through ELIXIR's participation as a case study research infrastructure. Provided experts for the working group. Answered their questionnaire. Presented (*Challenge of making large datasets available to broad user communities - lessons learned from COVID crisis*) at their 2022 virtual workshop⁴⁸ attended by government officials across the globe. The project's report (OECD, 2023b) mentions BY-COVID's MPOX (Monkeypox) pipeline and the COVID-19 Data Portal, the latter also being mentioned by a report on *COVID-19 and policy for science* (OECD, 2023a).

Next steps (if any):

Support their new project on *Research infrastructure ecosystems* through answering their questionnaire and providing experts for interviews with OECD staff. Through this, BY-COVID will aim to showcase how synergies between research infrastructures are essential for addressing complex challenges.

⁴⁸ <https://web.archive.oecd.org/2022-06-23/633796-vlri-issues-and-option.htm>

4.5.5 World Health Organisation (WHO)

Short description of the stakeholder:

The World Health Organization (WHO) is a specialised agency of the United Nations responsible for international public health. Established in 1948, its primary role is to direct and coordinate global health efforts, set health standards, and provide technical support to countries. In pandemic preparedness, WHO plays a crucial role by monitoring and assessing health threats, coordinating international responses, providing guidance on containment and treatment, and supporting the development and distribution of vaccines and treatments. Through initiatives like the International Health Regulations (IHR), WHO helps countries build capacities to detect, report, and respond to public health emergencies, ensuring a collaborative global approach to health crises.

Website: <https://www.who.int/>

Geographic scope: Europe

Aim(s) of the engagement: Showcase the opportunities and possibilities of the outputs of BY-COVID for the aims of WHO and their initiatives.

Relevant BY-COVID Task(s) or work package(s): Task 6.3 *Engage with intergovernmental policy-makers and funders*

BY-COVID focal partner(s): EMBL-EBI, Sciensano

Summary of engagement activities and related outcomes:

Several interactions and engagements with the WHO were registered. The table below shows a selection of the most important:

Date	Year	Interaction	Relevant mention
12-07-2022	2022	Policy Document Accelerating access to genomics for global health: promotion, implementation, collaboration, and ethical, legal, and social issues: a report of the WHO Science Council	Mention of the COVID-19 Data Portal ⁴⁹ .
11-11-2021	2011	Workshop Monitoring the wider impacts of COVID-19 on population health, workshop as part of the 14th European Public Health Conference	Mention of the COVID-19 Data Portal and BY-COVID project ⁵⁰ .
18-11-2021	2021	Presentation	Mention of the

⁴⁹ <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240052857>

⁵⁰ https://academic.oup.com/eurpub/article/31/Supplement_3/ckab164.173/6405690

		WHO Science Council Workshop Series: Accelerating access to genomic technologies for global health	COVID-19 Data Portal ⁵¹ .
19-11-2021		Consultation Response WHO-led Technical consultation session: 'Approaches to handling genetic sequence data for the future pandemic system'	Participation of the project PI and scientific lead ⁵² .

Next steps (if any): Keep the attention of the WHO office on the potentials of the Data Portal and follow up closely with the HIN to pinpoint where the outputs of BY-COVID can aid in their mission, even after the BY-COVID project ends. To ensure this, the outputs of BY-COVID should be easily findable on the homepage of By-COVID in an easy digestible format (one-pagers, flyers). In addition, there is a shared responsibility of all BY-COVID consortium partners to include the BY-COVID outputs in their work and outreach activities.

4.5.6 World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH)

Short description of the stakeholder:

WOAH is the global authority on animal health. It is an intergovernmental organisation, focused on transparently disseminating information on animal diseases, improving animal health globally and thus building a safer, healthier, and more sustainable world.

Website: <https://www.woah.org/en/home/>

Geographic scope: 183 Countries around the world

Aim(s) of the engagement:

To establish a framework for collaboration between BY-COVID and WOAH to enhance data sharing and interoperability between WAHIS and BY-COVID platforms. WAHIS is the global animal health reference database of the WOAH. WAHIS data reflects the validated information reported by the Veterinary Services on terrestrial and aquatic Listed diseases in domestic animals and wildlife, as well as on emerging diseases and zoonoses. WAHIS includes SARS-CoV2 data from animals as well as interactive mapping tools and dashboards to support data consultation, visualisation, and extraction of officially validated animal health data.

Relevant BY-COVID Task(s) or work package(s): Task 6.3 *Engage with intergovernmental policy-makers and funders* ; WP3 *COVID-19 integration platform*

BY-COVID focal partner(s): IZSLER, HSM

⁵¹<https://www.who.int/news-room/events/detail/2021/11/05/default-calendar/who-science-council-workshop-series-accelerating-access-to-genomic-technologies-for-global-health>

⁵²<https://www.who.int/news-room/events/detail/2021/11/19/default-calendar/technical-consultation-session-approaches-to-handling-genetic-sequence-data-for-the-future-pandemic-system>

Summary of engagement activities and related outcomes:

Two meetings were organised to address the issue of data sharing and interoperability between the WAHIS and BY-COVID platforms. During the initial meeting, WOAHA highlighted that WAHIS presently lacks the status of an open resource platform with API access for users to dynamically extract data. However, they revealed ongoing efforts towards developing a new version to incorporate these functionalities. In the subsequent call, WOAHA outlined the technical hurdles encountered in ensuring data stability, particularly concerning versioning and capacity limitations. They emphasised their active pursuit in resolving these challenges, including transitioning to a data warehouse approach. Key action points emerged, including WOAHA's commitment to sharing available documentation with BY-COVID. Meanwhile, the BY-COVID team pledged to assess this information to identify potential use cases for the Portal.

Next steps (if any): Further discussions are planned, dependent on WAHIS' technical progress.

4.5.7 G7 Open Science Working Group

Short description of the stakeholder:

The Group of Seven (G7) is an intergovernmental political and economic forum consisting of Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, the United Kingdom and the United States. Its Open Science Working Group aims to promote the efficient processing and sharing of research data across the G7 and beyond, and address barriers that hinder scientific cooperation and slow the ability to respond to crises, such as pandemics.

Website: N/A

Geographic scope: global

Aim(s) of the engagement:

Ensure that the BY-COVID project and its outputs are visible to policy-makers (especially those dealing with research infrastructures), and ideally appreciated and endorsed.

Relevant BY-COVID Task(s) or work package(s): Task 6.3 *Engage with intergovernmental policy-makers and funders*

BY-COVID focal partner(s): ELIXIR Hub, EMBL-EBI

Summary of engagement activities and related outcomes:

Selected to write a case study on COVID-19 for the *Sub-Working Group on Interoperability and Sustainability of Infrastructures*, on existing examples of national and international data-sharing infrastructure related to the pandemic, including lessons learned, barriers,

challenges, and opportunities. This resulted in mention of BY-COVID and the COVID-19 Data Portal in their activity report (Sub-Working Group on Interoperability and Sustainability of Infrastructures, 2022). BY-COVID experts also engaged with, and supported the work of, the UK's government department of Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy (BEIS), which *intended to add depth and precision to the G7 Open Science Working Group's recommendations on data sharing across borders, and related research practice and cultural issues*⁵³, in which report (Johnson et al., 2022) the COVID-19 Data Portal is mentioned.

Next steps (if any): BY-COVID will continue to seek opportunities to support relevant G7 work streams.

5. Impacts in the policy sphere

Policy impact was monitored collectively through a dedicated spreadsheet tracking mentions of the project and its outputs in European and international policy documents (Figure 7). This was supplemented by targeted searches in Overton.io, to capture any mention that could be missing. Selected examples of reports containing mentions are shown in Figures 8 and 9 - they mainly relate to the project being mentioned or the COVID-19 Data Platform. A preliminary version of the latter was created before the project started, hence it had sufficient time to make an impact in the policy sphere. This contrasts with other project outputs, such as the Infectious Diseases Toolkit, which were born during project life and which will more likely get mentions after the end of the project.

⁵³<https://www.research-consulting.com/intelligent-open-science-lessons-learned-from-genomic-viral-data-sharing-during-the-covid-19-pandemic/>

Figure 7. Number of European and international policy documents mentioning BY-COVID and its outputs (October 2021 to September 2024)

Figure 8. Selected examples of European and international policy documents mentioning the project and its outputs.

Figure 9. Example of a mention of the COVID-19 Data Platform in a briefing note to Ministers, in the context of the Swedish Presidency of the Council of the European Union (2023).

The full list of such policy documents (Annex 1) provides insights into the scale and magnitude of visibility and influence of BY-COVID and its outputs in the policy sphere. Although much effort was expended by the BY-COVID consortium to arrive at such results, mentions in policy documents are impacts that are very much outside of the project’s sphere of control, and hence constitute project impact.

6. Conclusion and next steps

Work Package 6 aimed to engage, train, and build capacity with stakeholders to support the development of an efficient infrastructure for European preparedness against COVID-19 and other infectious diseases. This goal was achieved through four standalone yet complementary tasks (6.1 to 6.4), each aligning with the project’s overarching objectives.

BY-COVID has successfully achieved its objectives of being visible and influential, and hence impactful, among national and international stakeholders. The project’s extensive reach is evidenced by mentions in over 20 European and international policy documents, along with multiple invited presentations at high-level scientific and policy conferences of particular relevance to the project. These accomplishments are evidenced by a significant number of consultation responses, targeted actions to increase visibility, and a comprehensive list of mentions and presentations detailed in relevant tasks (6.1, 6.2, 6.3).

The insights gained from this stakeholder engagement monitoring exercise were instrumental in developing deliverable D6.1.

Building on the momentum of a high-level event in Brussels in 2023, co-organised with Task 7.4, which brought together key opinion leaders to discuss open science for pandemic preparedness in the context of BY-COVID, a follow-up event is planned for September 2024. This will ensure continued dialogue and engagement on this critical topic. The cumulative efforts and strategic initiatives have established BY-COVID as a pivotal player in the realm of pandemic preparedness and open science, laying a strong foundation for future endeavours and collaborations. Looking forward, the legacy of BY-COVID will continue onto projects such as EVORA and the European Partnership for Pandemic Preparedness BE-READY.

7. Deviations from the Description of Action

No deviations from the description of action were reported.

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9. Annexes

9.1 Annex 1

Policy documents mentioning BY-COVID and its outputs.

Year	Policy document	Source	Relevant mentions	Hyperlinks
2021	Study on the use of real-world data (RWD) for research, clinical care, regulatory decision-making, health technology assessment, and policy-making : final report and recommendations	European Commission	Mention of the COVID-19 Data Portal	Link ⁵⁴
2021	Introducing HERA, the European Health Emergency preparedness and Response Authority, the next step towards completing the European Health Union	European Commission	Mention of the COVID-19 Data Portal	Link ⁵⁵
2021	Recommendations on how to make R&I a driver for sustainable development in AU (African Union)-EU relations	European Commission	COVID-19 Data Portal, Sars-CoV-2 data hubs	Link ⁵⁶
2021	European research & innovation days, Conference report : 23-24 June 2021	European Commission	Mention of the COVID-19 Data Portal.	Link ⁵⁷

⁵⁴ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/6f758166-2198-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁵⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/default/files/preparedness_response/docs/hera_2021_comm_en.pdf

⁵⁶ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/db6ccbe8-9070-11ec-b4e4-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-251417867>

⁵⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/599fb1da-5bc7-11ec-91ac-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-245732411>

2022	Manifesto for EU COVID-19 research: Maximising the accessibility of research results in the fight against COVID-19	European Commission	Signatories ⁵⁸ commit to "make COVID-19 research data available through the European COVID-19 Data Platform"	Link ⁵⁹
2022	Maximising investments in health research - FAIR data for a coordinated COVID-19 response : workshop report	European Commission	Mention of BY-COVID, the COVID-19 Data Portal and FAIRsharing	Link ⁶⁰
2022	Selected to write a case study on COVID-19 for the G7 "OSWG (open science working group) Sub-Working Group on Interoperability and Sustainability of Infrastructures", on existing examples of national and international data-sharing infrastructure related to the pandemic, including lessons learned, barriers, challenges, and opportunities.	G7	Mention of BY-COVID and the COVID-19 Data Portal	(not public)
2022	Study on an infrastructure and data ecosystem supporting the impact assessment of the European Health Data Space	European Commission	Several BY-COVID partners mentioned by name.	Link ⁶¹
2022	From intent to impact: Investigating the effects of open sharing commitments	Wellcome Trust	Mention COVID-19 Data Portal	Link ⁶²
2022	Accelerating access to genomics for global health: promotion, implementation, collaboration, and ethical, legal, and social issues: a report of the WHO Science Council	World Health Organisation (WHO)	Mention of the COVID-19 Data Portal.	Link ⁶³

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https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/research-area/health-research-and-innovation/coronavirus-research-and-innovation/covid-research-manifesto_en

⁵⁹ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/b67a8ecc-8a29-11ec-8c40-01aa75ed71a1/language-en#>

⁶⁰ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/f023acef-ba07-11ec-b6f4-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁶¹ https://ec.europa.eu/health/publications/study-infrastructure-and-data-ecosystem-supporting-impact-assessment-european-health-data-space_en

⁶² <https://zenodo.org/record/6620854#.YqySQ-zMIII>

⁶³ <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240052857>

2022	Intelligent open science: A case study of viral genomic data sharing during the COVID-19 pandemic	BEIS (The UK Government Department of Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy) for the G7 Open Science Working Group	Mention of the COVID-19 Data Portal.	Additional information ⁶⁴ ; Link ⁶⁵
2022	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)	European Commission	Mention of the COVID-19 Data Portal	Link ⁶⁶
2023	HORIZON-HLTH-2023-DISEASE-03-07 Relationship between infections and non- communicable diseases	Horizon Europe	Applicants are encouraged to link to the COVID-19 Data Platform	Link ⁶⁷
2023	TRE-FX project (2023-02-01 to 2023-09-01)	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	Project funded by UKRI as spin-off from a Work Packages 2 and 4 collaboration	Link ⁶⁸

⁶⁴ <https://www.research-consulting.com/intelligent-open-science-lessons-learned-from-genomic-viral-data-sharing-during-the-covid-19-pandemic/>

⁶⁵ https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1116781/intelligent-open-science.pdf

⁶⁶ <https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/SRIA-1.1-final.pdf>

⁶⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-hlth-2023-disease-03-07;callCode=null;freeTextSearchKeyword=;matchWholeText=true;typeCodes=1,2,8;statusCodes=31094501,31094502;programmePeriod=null;programCcm2Id=43108390;programDivisionCode=43108557;focusAreaCode=null;destinationGroup=null;missionGroup=null;geographicalZonesCode=null;programmeDivisionProspect=null;startDateLte=null;startDateGte=null;crossCuttingPriorityCode=null;cpvCode=null;performanceOfDelivery=null;sortQuery=sortStatus;orderBy=asc;onlyTenders=false;topicListKey=topicSearchTablePageState>

⁶⁸ <https://trefx.uk/>

2023	Informal meeting of Ministers responsible for Higher education, Research and Innovation - Policy debate – Briefing note on research infrastructures in the digital transition – maximizing the benefit of research data	Swedish Presidency of the Council of the European Union	Mention of the COVID-19 Data Portal	Link ⁶⁹
2023	Very large research infrastructures: policy issues and options	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD)	Mentions of the COVID-19 Data portal, and BY-COVID (specifically its MPOX "monkeypox" pipeline)	Link ⁷⁰
2023	New portal a key tool for better global pathogen surveillance	European Commission	BY-COVID selected by CORDIS EU Research Results to be featured in a news article	Link ⁷¹
2023	HORIZON-HLTH-2024-DISEASE-08-12 Pandemic preparedness and response: Maintaining the European partnership for pandemic preparedness	European Commission	BY-COVID mentioned as a project that consortia should build on	Link ⁷²

⁶⁹https://swedish-presidency.consilium.europa.eu/media/ffepo0ad/draft-background-paper_-_policy-debate-informal-compet-research-infrastructures-final.pdf

⁷⁰<https://doi.org/10.1787/2b93187f-en>

⁷¹https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/446128-new-portal-a-key-tool-for-better-global-pathogen-surveillance?WT.mc_id=exp

⁷²<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-hlth-2024-disease-08-12;callCode=null;freeTextSearchKeyword=;matchWholeText=true;typeCodes=1,2,8;statusCodes=31094501,31094502;programmePeriod=null;programCcm2Id=43108390;programDivisionCode=43108557;focusAreaCode=null;destinationGroup=null;missionGroup=null;geographicalZonesCode=null;programmeDivisionProspect=null;startDateLte=null;startDateGte=null;crossCuttingPriorityCode=null;cpvCode=null;performanceOfDelivery=null;sortQuery=sortStatus;orderBy=asc;onlyTenders=false;topicListKey=topicSearchTablePageState>

2023	OECD Science, Technology and Policy papers: COVID-19 and policy for science	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD)	Mention of the COVID-19 Data Portal	Link ⁷³
2023	CORDIS results pack on research infrastructures in Europe	European Commission	Mentions of BY-COVID project and the COVID-19 Data Platform	Link ⁷⁴
2023	Evaluation study on the relevance and internal coherence of Horizon 2020 and its policy mix - Publications Office of the EU	European Commission	Mention of the COVID-19 Data Platform	Link ⁷⁵
2023	Evaluation study of the European framework programmes for research and innovation for excellent science	European Commission	Mentions of the COVID-19 Data Platform	Link ⁷⁶
2024	Draft Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) on Pandemic Preparedness	European Commission	Mentions of the COVID-19 Data Platform and also BY-COVID project	(confidential)
2024	ESFRI Landscape Analysis 2024	ESFRI	Mentions of the BY-COVID project	Link ⁷⁷

⁷³<https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/docserver/8f86e60b-en.pdf?expires=1689858630&id=id&acname=guest&checksum=7414840857787D7A0F9C390B9A9C66D0>

⁷⁴http://publications.europa.eu/resource/cellar/1896a69c-9000-11ee-8aa6-01aa75ed71a1.0001.01/DOC_1

⁷⁵<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/bdb2c96a-8a88-11ee-99ba-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF>

⁷⁶<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/048c35b7-149e-11ee-806b-01aa75ed71a1>

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